

Conditional Probability $P(p/x)$ versus Hydrodynamic Approach to the Bound Schrodinger Equation

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In a previous note (1), we argue one may formulate the bound state Schrodinger equation using conditional probabilities $P(p/x) = a(p)f(p,x)/W(x)$ i.e

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m a(p) f(p,x)] / W(x) + V(x) = E$$

where the normalization constant $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ and $a(p)$ is to be determined. We further argue that $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ because $P(x)$ (as density) may only exist within a Δx region (in 1 D) and stochastic hits from a potential change an $\exp(ip_1 x)$ momentum state to an $\exp(ip_2 x)$ one within Δx . Thus, one has all p_1, p_2 combinations leading to a $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$.

In the literature, one often finds derivations of the Schrodinger equation based on the Boltzmann transport equation. Thus, a distribution function $f(p,x,t)$ is defined (p, x are vectors) such that $\int dx f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x)$. Then, standard Boltzmann fluid conservation type equations are used. In this note, we focus on a derivation presented in (2). In this derivation, one may use spatial density exclusively for the bound state case. In other words, there is no need to ever introduce the idea of a wavefunction. In this note, we argue that the main point of the hydrodynamic Boltzmann approach (2) is to assume that $\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} [\ln(\text{density})]$ is proportional to Average(momentum) ((1)). This suggests the density or square root of density contains $\exp(ipx)$ terms and describes dynamics. As a result, the "hydrodynamic approach" with such an assumption becomes identical to the conditional probability one. What seems unusual is that one has $f(x,p,t)$ in the hydrodynamic case, so it is not clear why one would integrate over dp to obtain $\text{density}(x)$ and then take spatial derivatives of a function of density to obtain information about a velocity average. Rather, it seems that $f(x,p,t)$ would be used exclusively for velocity function averages. In other words, a new momentum distribution $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that $\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) = W(x)$ emerges and this is not the same as the original $f(p,x,t)$.

We argue that by assuming ((1)), one is really using $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p P(p/x)$ or a conditional probability picture.

In this note, we focus on the time independent Schrodinger case, although (2) presents a hydrodynamic derivation of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. In short, we try to show that two distributions are used in the hydrodynamic case, $f(p,x,t)$ such that $\text{density} = \text{Sum over } p f(p,x,t)$ and $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that $W(x) = \text{square root density (for bound states)} = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, although only the former seems to be officially acknowledged. In the conditional probabilistic approach, one uses the distribution $a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, the hydrodynamic approach, at least classically, seems to be associated with stochastic collisions among particles while for the quantum single particle case, we argue that there is a momentum distribution at x and that it interacts (or receives) stochastic momentum hits from the potential $V(x)$ where $V(x)$ is only an average.

Conditional Probability Approach of (1)

The conditional probability approach considers a distribution of momentum at a point x i.e. different time points of a single particle at x . The distribution is created by $V(x)$ which is an average form and may be expressed as:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k(kx) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, $-d/dx V(x)$ yields: $\text{Sum over } k \quad k V_k(kx)$ so the force from a $V_k(kx)$ term adds a momentum of k .

$$P(p/x) = [\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x)] / [\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x)] \quad \text{where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) f(p,x) \quad ((3))$$

At a point x , the probability for a p is: $a(p) f(p,x) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the normalization constant. If one considers $P(x)$ as a density, it exists within a range Δx . Within this range, one may have a p_1 collide with a $V_k(kx)$ to form a p_1+k . Any combination is possible, so we argue that $P(x) = \text{Sum } p_1, p_2 \quad a(p_1) f(p_1,x) a(p_2) f(p_2,x) = W(x)W(x)$ with $\text{Integral } dx \quad W(x)W(x)=1$. Then: $P(p) = \text{Sum over } x \quad P(p/x) P(x) = \text{Sum over } x \quad a(p_1)a(p_2) f(p_1,x) f(p_2,x)$. We argue that $f(p,x)$ forms an orthonormal basis.

$$\text{At a point } x: \quad [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^*p/2m a(p) f(p,x)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

If one multiplies by $W(x)$, one has a term $V(x)W(x)$. Physically, $V_k(kx)$ combines with $f(p,x)$ to create an $f(p+k,x)$ so we argue that $V_k(kx)$ and $f(p,x)$ are of the same form i.e. functions of momentum $*x$ and that $f(p_1x)f(p_2x) = f((p_1+p_2)x)$. This leads to $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ as a solution. Using this in ((4)) leads to the bound state Schrodinger equation.

A main point we wish to make is that $\text{Sum over } p \quad P(p/x) = W(x)$. This is different from the Boltzmann transport approach in which $\text{Sum over } p \quad f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t)$.

Hydrodynamic Approach of (2)

In (2), a Boltzmann transport ensemble distribution of $f(p,x,t)$ is used where:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t)$$

The idea in the Boltzmann transport scenario seems to be that different particles collide stochastically with each other. The potential $V(x)$ acts in a deterministic way and does not give stochastic hits to the particle. In a single particle quantum bound state, however, there is only one particle and we argue the potential is stochastic.

In (2), the average over p is defined by:

$$\langle G(p,x,t) \rangle_p = \frac{[\text{Sum over } p \ G(p,x,t) f(p,x,t)]}{[\text{Sum over } p \ f(p,x,t)]}$$

Next, it is assumed that: $df/dt + vdf/dx + F/m df/dv = C(f)$ and that:

$$d/dt (m \text{ density } u_i) + d(\text{density } s_{ij}) / dx_k + \text{density } dV/dx = 0 \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } V \text{ is the potential and}$$

$$u_i = \langle p_i/m \rangle_p \text{ and } s_{ij} = \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle_p \quad ((5b))$$

This follows from traditional Boltzmann transport theory and a conserved quantity. Next, the second term of ((5)) is linked to a “quantum potential” or a fluid potential $W(x)$ i.e. a mathematical potential (not the real potential $V(x)$):

$$S_{jk} d \ln(\text{density}) / dx_k + ds_{jk} / dx_k = dW/dx_j \quad \text{i.e. } dW/dx_j \text{ is like a quantum force.}$$

In (2) it is then assumed there is a solution for which:

$$s_{ij} = d/dx_j d/dx_k \ln(\text{density})^b \quad \text{where } b \text{ is a constant} \quad ((6))$$

If one examines the definition of s_{ij} , however, it is based on expectation values of v_i, v_j terms (see ((5b))) which should be taken with $f(p,x,t)$, not with the derivative of density. Thus a new approach is taken in (2).

The key idea of (2), it seems, is to suggest a specific solution along the lines of:

$$.5 d/dx_i \ln(\text{density}) = \text{Average } (p_i/m) \quad ((7))$$

In (2), this is written in a slightly different manner using a factor of .25 not .5, but nevertheless ((7)) seems to be the main idea. Thus, the idea seems to be to try to “force” average velocity information out of the density by using spatial derivatives. This seems to be motivated by considering an average of p_i/m at a point x (which is a function of x) and seeing how this average changes with x under the influence of a spatial $d/dx W(x)$ force (not the real force but rather a mathematical construct). In (1), we consider an average of $p^2/2m$ at x (a function of x) and try to consider how it changes under the influence of $-dV/dx$ (where V is stochastic), but do not use $f(x,p,t)$ as the momentum distribution, but rather $a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In fact, for the bound state case, one may describe the Schrodinger equation in (2) strictly in terms of density(x), there is no need to even introduce the idea of a wavefunction, yet it is the wavefunction which contains the momentum distribution.

$$((7)) \text{ should also equal } \frac{[\text{Sum over } p_i \ p_i/m f(p,x,t)]}{[\text{Sum over } p \ f(p,x,t)]}$$

Thus, a spatial derivative of density(x) yields average velocity(momentum) information even though momentum has been integrated out of $f(p,x,t)$ when forming the density(x) in the first

place. Usually in classical statistical mechanics, if one integrates $f(p,x,t)$ over p , one loses p information and is left only with spatial density information.

In (2), a function of the spatial density carries information about average momenta. If one lets $W(x)W(x)=\text{density}(x)$ as in quantum mechanics, then ((7)) is equivalent to:

$$d/dx \ln(W) = \langle p \rangle / m. \quad ((7b))$$

This, however, suggests that $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$, but the distribution $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is not $f(p,x,t)$. Furthermore, $f(p,x,t)$ is unnormalized in (2) so $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx) = W(x)$ and not density while $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t)$.

If ((7b)) does not seem immediately evident, it should be noted that the assumption (or second solution) ((7)) used in (2) leads directly to the Schrodinger equation in terms of $W(x)$. For the bound case, one has: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W + V(x) = E$.

Thus, one may see that for both ((7)) and $\langle p \rangle$ and the bound Schrodinger equation, a distribution function $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ (unnormalized) seems to be used, in fact it is the $P(p/x)$ distribution.

In other words, there seem to be two averaging schemes or distributions being used:

$$\langle p \rangle_p = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p f(p,x,t)] / [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f(p,x,t)] \quad \text{but also}$$

$$\langle p \rangle_p = \frac{dW(x)/dx}{W(x)} = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$$

$$\text{where density} = W(x)W(x) = \int f(p,x,t) dp$$

Thus, in (2) one begins with $f(p,x,t)$ from the Boltzmann transport equation, but uses assumption ((7)) to create what seems to be the $P(p/x)$ momentum distribution based on $W(x)$.

We argue that $W(x)$ is the key function in the picture and it is d/dx of this function which yields dynamical information. $W(x)$ appears as a normalization in $P(p/x)$ and it is $P(p/x)$ which is the momentum distribution in question or rather $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ if one uses the unnormalized version.

Thus in (2), $f(p,x,t)$ seems to disappear and a result based strictly on $\text{density}(x)$ for a bound state replaces it. Average values of p , however, are based on a spatial derivative of $.5 \ln[\text{sqrt}(\text{density})]$, so this seems to be a different theory from the initial hydrodynamic one. In short, it seems to be consistent with the conditional probability picture described above. It is interesting, however, that it may be formulated using hydrodynamic equations, however, these equations start with the idea of an $f(p,x,t)$. By introducing a new solution using ((7)), one shifts away from $f(p,x,t)$ and finds momentum averages from a new distribution function $P(p/x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } P(p/x)$. $f(p,x,t)$, in a loose sense, is associated with density averages.

Hydrodynamical Approach to the Bound Schrodinger Equation and Density

In this section, we wish to show that the hydrodynamical approach of (2) may be described strictly in terms of density(x) with no need to introduce a wavefunction.

For the time dependent Schrodinger equation, one has from (2) the form, with d=density

$$E = V(x) + (-1/4m) \{ 1/d \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} d - [\frac{d}{dx} \ln(d)]^2 \} = V(x) - (.5/mW) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$$

and $d=W*W$

Thus, for the bound state case, everything may be presented in terms of density and one would not really see the wavefunction at all. (Later in (2), expectation values of operators are formulated in terms of the wavefunction. Also, in (2) the Schrodinger equation is written in terms of the wavefunction, but for the bound case, there is no need to do this.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the hydrodynamical approach to deriving the Schrodinger equation in (2) seems to be based on the key idea that a spatial derivative of a function of density may yield information about average momentum. Thus, one may bypass $f(p,x,t)$ which would normally such an average. It seems that in doing so, one is really using: $.5 \frac{d}{dx} \ln(\text{density})$ to obtain an average velocity, but this is equivalent to: $[\frac{d}{dx} W(x)] / W(x)$ and $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus, $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ appears to be the momentum distribution in question and this is not $f(p,x,t)$.

By assuming that a spatial derivative of a function of density yields average momentum (as done in (2)), one obtains a theory which yields equivalent results as one using conditional probability $P(p/x)$.

Thus, two distributions seem to be used in the hydrodynamic approach of (2). First, there is $f(p,x,t)$ such that $\text{Sum over } p f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x)$. $f(p,x,t)$ is the starting point of the whole hydrodynamic approach as it satisfies a certain differential equation which may be converted into various other differential equations based on conserved quantities. One of these differential equations leads to another "hidden" distribution which may be used to calculate average momentum, namely $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) = W(x)$ such that $\text{density} = W(x)W(x)$. (This "hidden" distribution may also be used to calculate average kinetic energy which may be added to $V(x)$ and set equal to E in bound state problems.) Thus, one may ask why one would not start with this "hidden" momentum distribution in the first place. Furthermore, the hydrodynamic approach (in classical statistical mechanics) assumes stochastic collisions between particles, not a stochastic potential. In single particle quantum

mechanics, there is only one particle and we argue that not only does it follow a momentum distribution at each x (at different times), but that the potential gives the particle stochastic hits. Nevertheless, it is interesting that the classical Boltzmann transport approach contains a “hidden” quantum solution as proposed in (2), it seems. It should be noted that in order to obtain the quantum solution in (2), one needs to force a term related to average π at x (i.e. a function of x) to act as if they were affected by a mathematical potential $W(x)$ (the real potential is $V(x)$).

References

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